

Attempted Synthesis of Dialkylaminoethylethers of α -(2-Phenylindol-3-yl)Benzylalcohols: Unexpected Formation of α' - α -Di(2-phenylindol-3-yl)Dibenzylethers

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α -(2-Phenylindol-3-yl) benzyl alcohols were reacted with dialkylaminoethyl chloride in presence of sodium hydride, with a view to synthesise dialkylaminoethyl ethers of α -(indol-3-yl) benzyl alcohols. Unexpectedly, this reaction yielded various α , α' -di (2-phenylindol-3-yl) dibenzyl ethers whose structures were confirmed on the basis of their UV, IR, PMR and mass spectral data.

SOME dimethylaminoethyl ethers of α -(indol-3-yl)-benzyl alcohols have been reported¹ to possess notable antiallergic and sedative properties. Hence, in the present paper our attempts to synthesise various dialkylaminoethyl ethers of α -(1-substituted-5-methoxy-2-phenylindol-3-yl) benzyl alcohols for

pharmacological evaluation from the 1-substituted-3-benzoyl-5-methoxy-2-phenylindoles reported by us earlier² are described.

The 1-substituted-2-benzoyl-5-methoxy-2-phenylindoles (1-4) and their benzindole analogues (5-7)

SCHEME 1

Ketones	Alcohols	Ethers	R
1	8	15	$-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$
2	9	16	$-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$
3	10	17	$-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$
4	11	18	$-\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$
5	12	19	$-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$
6	13	20	$-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$
7	14	21	$-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$

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were reduced with lithium aluminium hydride to obtain the benzyl alcohols (8-14). α -(1-*iso*-Butyl-5-

methoxy-2-phenylindol-3-yl)benzyl alcohol (8) was reacted with dimethylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride or diethylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride in presence of sodium hydride using dry benzene or toluene as solvent. Surprisingly, this reaction did not yield the desired dialkylaminoethyl ethers but gave a colourless product (15) which does not possess basic properties.

The IR spectrum of (15) revealed the absence of hydroxyl function and its UV absorption maxima were observed at 226 and 300 nm, which are characteristic of indole moiety. Analytical results of (15) were found to be in agreement with the molecular formula $C_{52}H_{52}N_2O_2$. This was confirmed by its mass spectrum which gave a molecular ion peak at m/e 752. The principal fragmentation pattern of (15) indicated it to be an ether and is in conformity with a general path reported³ for the ethers. Molecular ion (m/e 752) (18%) lost a lightly substituted substituent located on α -carbon of the dibenzyl ether (15) as a radical ($C_{19}H_{20}NO$) to give an ion (m/e 474) (100%). Therefore, the product obtained must be α, α' -di(1-*iso*-butyl-5-methoxy-2-phenylindol-3-yl)dibenzyl ether (15) and the study of its PMR spectral data fully supports this structure. Two *iso*-butyl groups attached to indole N showed a hump around 9.42 τ (methyl protons), another hump at 8.07 τ (central methine protons) and two doublets at 6.22 and 6.28 τ (J 7Hz) due to the methylene protons. The C-5 methoxyls gave a singlet at 6.43 τ . The signals for α - and α' -protons were observed as singlets at 4.22 and 4.34 τ while α -proton of its precursor alcohol (8) showed a singlet at 4.08 τ . An upfield shift shown by the signals of α - and α' -protons confirmed the dibenzyl ether structure and an analogous upfield shift of the α -proton signal on etherification of the alcohol function has been noted by Narayanan and Iyer⁴. Aromatic region (2.4–3.5 τ) accounted for the presence of twenty six aromatic protons.

Similarly, various dibenzyl ethers (16–21) were obtained from the corresponding α -(2-phenylindol-3-yl)-benzyl alcohols (9–14). When the reaction was carried out using excess quantity of dimethylaminoethyl chloride (or diethylaminoethyl chloride) or their hydrochlorides, the same dibenzyl ethers (15–21) were isolated. Various α -(2-phenylindol-3-yl)benzyl alcohols (8–14) were reacted under reflux in benzene or toluene with sodium hydride but the ether formation did not take place.

The mass spectrum of the dibenzyl ether (20) showed that this compound has followed two principal fragmentation paths under electron impact. The first path described in scheme 2 involves McLafferty rearrangement⁵. The fairly stable molecular ion (m/e 852) (91%) lost a ketone ($C_{30}H_{27}NO_2$) leading to a base peak at m/e 419.

The second path is a general way of fragmentation of ethers³ as described for (15). Further, the PMR data of (20) supported its structure as α, α' -di(1-*n*-butyl-5-methoxy-2-phenyl-1H-benz[g]indol-3-yl) dibenzyl ether.

The PMR spectrum of α -(1-*iso*-butyl-5-methoxy-2-phenyl-1H-benz[g]indol-3-yl) benzyl alcohol (12)

SCHEME 2

shows interesting features in the sense that the two methyls belonging to *iso*-butyl group located on indole N display magnetic non-equivalence. However, analogous methyls of the *iso*-butyl group belonging to α -(1-*iso*-butyl-5-methoxy-2-phenylindol-3-yl) benzyl alcohol (8) show a doublet (9.34 τ) implying their equivalence. Hence, it is felt that the magnetic non-equivalence shown by these two methyl groups (9.35 and 9.4 τ , J 7Hz) of the benzindole (12) results from the restricted rotation about the CH–CH₂ bond of the 1-*iso*-butyl group which in turn is due to the presence of C-6, C-7 benzene ring.

Experimental

The 1-substituted-3-benzoyl-5-methoxy-2-phenylindoles (1–4) and their benzindole analogues (5–7) were prepared as described earlier.²

α -(1-*iso*-Butyl-5-methoxy-2-phenylindol-3-yl)benzyl alcohol (8) :

1-*iso*-Butyl-3-benzoyl-5-methoxy-2-phenylindole (1) (4 g) in dry tetrahydrofuran (50 ml) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride (1.5 g) in dry ether (100 ml) by stirring at room temperature for 2 hr. On cooling with ice, the complex was decomposed with the addition of water (1.5 ml), sodium hydroxide solution (1.5 ml, 15%) and water (3 ml). The separated white precipitate was filtered off and washed with ether (50 ml). The combined filtrate was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the residue obtained on removing the solvent was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether to get pure α -(2-phenylindol-3-yl) benzyl alcohol (8).

Various α -(2-phenylindol-3-yl)benzyl alcohols (8–14) prepared from 3-benzoyl-2-phenylindoles(1–7) by following the above procedure are described in Table 1.

α, α' -Di(1-*iso*-butyl-5-methoxy-2-phenylindol-3-yl)dibenzyl ether (15) :

Sodium hydride (50% dispersion, 0.48 g, 0.01 mole) was added to a solution of α -(1-*iso*-butyl-5-methoxy-

TABLE 1. α -(1-SUBSTITUTED-5-METHOXY-2-PHENYLINDOL-3-YL) BENZYL ALCOHOLS (8-11) AND THEIR BENZINDOLE ANALOGUES (12-14)

Com- pound	1-Substi- tuent R	M.P. °C	TLC* (Rf value)	Found %	Formula	Requires %	UV* Spectra λ_{max}^{EtOH} nm (log e)	IR Spectra ν_{OH}^{Nujol}	PMR+ Spectral data τ
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
8	<i>iso</i> -Butyl	171(d)	0.40	C, 80.95 H, 6.90 N, 3.70	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ NO ₂	C, 81.01 H, 7.06 N, 3.63	226(4.46) 295(4.16)	3560m 3440s	6.14, 8.07 & 9.34 (-CH ₂ CH [(CH ₂ CH(CH ₃) ₂] d, m & d, J7), 7.85 (OH, s); 4.08 (α -H, s); 6.32 (C-5O CH ₃ , s); 2.4-3.25 (ArH, m); On D ₂ O exchange OH signal vanished.
9	<i>n</i> -Butyl	117(d)	0.512	C, 80.75 H, 7.21 N, 3.80	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ NO ₂	C, 81.01 H, 7.06 N, 3.63	230(4.54) 295(4.30)	3460s	—
10	<i>n</i> -Propyl	124(d)	0.471	C, 80.65 H, 6.55 N, 4.01	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ NO ₂	C, 80.83 H, 6.78 N, 3.77	227(4.37) 295(4.07)	3560m 3450s	—
11	Benzyl	104(d)	0.475	C, 82.81 H, 6.13 N, 3.32	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ NO ₂	C, 83.03 H, 6.01 N, 3.34	224(4.46) 298(4.16)	3480s	7.8 (OH, d, J4); 4.03 (α -H, d, J4) 6.33 (C-5 OCH ₃ , s); 4.8 (-CH ₂ , s); 2.34-3.34 (ArH, m). On D ₂ O Exchange OH signal vanished & doublet (4.03) collapsed to a singlet.
12	<i>iso</i> -Butyl	160(d)	0.525	C, 82.93 H, 6.92 N, 3.34	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ NO ₂	C, 82.73 H, 6.71 N, 3.22	220(4.47) 280(4.59)	3550m 3430s	9.4, 9.35, 7.74 & 5.76 (<i>iso</i> -Butyl, d, d, m, d, J7); 7.84 (OH, d, J4); 4.03 (α -H, d); 6.23 (C-5O CH ₃ , s); 1.5-3.17 (ArH, m); 3.12 (C-4H, s); 1.68 (C-6H & C-9H, m).
13	<i>n</i> -Butyl	114(d)	0.50	C, 82.68 H, 6.48 N, 3.25	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ NO ₂	C, 82.73 H, 6.71 N, 3.22	222(4.54) 275(4.69)	3540m 3450m	7.78 br (OH, s); 4.07 br (α -H, s); 6.22 (C-5O CH ₃ , s); 9.26, 8.84, 8.24 & 5.65 (<i>n</i> -Butyl, deformed t, m, m & t, J7); 1.5-3.2 (ArH, m); 3.15 (C-4H, s); 1.7 C-6H & C-9H, m).
14	<i>n</i> -Propyl	131	0.558	C, 82.58 H, 6.70 N, 3.59	C ₂₉ H ₂₇ NO ₂	C, 82.63 H, 6.46 N, 3.32	222(4.42) 280(4.61)	3290s	7.8 (OH, d, J4); 4.1 (α -H, d); 6.2 (C-5O CH ₃ , s); 9.27, 8.1 & 5.68 (<i>n</i> -Propyl, t, m & t, J7); 1.54-3.16 (ArH, m); 3.14 (C-4H, s); (C-6H & C-9H, m).

* Silica gel G, Benzene-ethyl acetate (11 : 1) but (8 : 1) for 2 & 7 and (4 : 1) for 1.

** The UV spectra were recorded on ethanol solution.

+ The PMR spectra were recorded on Varian T 60 MHz spectrometer in CDCl₃ solutions using TMS as an internal standard; J values are in Hz; br, broadened; s, singlet, d, doublet, t triplet; m, multiplet.

2-phenylindol-3-yl)benzyl alcohol (8) (1.92 g, 0.005 mole) in dry benzene (25 ml) or dry toluene (25 ml) and the mixture was heated under reflux for 2 hr and then cooled to 50°. β -Dimethylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride (0.72 g, 0.005 mole) or β -diethylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride (0.88 g, 0.005 mole) was added to the above mixture and heated under reflux for 8-10 hr. On cooling, cold water (50 ml) was added to the mixture and extracted

with ether. Ether extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue obtained on removing solvent was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether to yield pure dibenzyl ether (15).

Various α, α' -di(2-phenylindol-3-yl)dibenzyl ethers (15-21) prepared from α -(2-phenylindol-3-yl)benzyl alcohols (8-14) by following the above procedure are described in Table 2.

TABLE 2. α - α' -DI(1-SUBSTITUTED-5-METHOXY-2-PHENYLINDOL-3-YL) DIBENZYL ETHERS (15-18) AND THEIR BENZINDOLE ANALOGUES (19-21)

Com- pound	M.P. °C	Found %	Formula	Requires %	UV* Spectra $\lambda_{\text{EtOH}}^{\text{max}}$ nm (log ϵ)	PMR Spectral data τ	Mass spectrum m/e (rel. abundance)
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
15	161	C, 82.78 H, 6.83 N, 3.84	C ₅₂ H ₅₂ N ₂ O ₃	C, 82.99 H, 6.92 N, 3.72	226(4.74) 300(4.46)	9.42, 8.07, 6.22 & 6.28 (<i>iso</i> -butyl, hump, hump & 2d, J7); 4.22 & 4.34 (α -H & α' -H, 2s); 6.43 (2C-5 OCH ₃ , s); 2.4-3.5 (ArH, 26H, m).	752 (M ⁺) (18%), 474 (M-C ₁₈ H ₂₀ NO) (100%).
16	162	C, 83.13 H, 7.08 N, 3.61	C ₅₂ H ₅₂ N ₂ O ₃	C, 82.99 H, 6.92 N, 3.72	225(4.65) 300(4.37)	—	—
17	165	C, 82.71 H, 6.82 N, 3.98	C ₅₀ H ₄₈ N ₂ O ₃	C, 82.88 H, 6.63 N, 3.87	218(4.80) 300(4.32)	—	—
18	186	C, 85.06 H, 5.76 N, 3.58	C ₅₈ H ₄₈ N ₂ O ₃	C, 84.87 H, 5.85 N, 3.42	224(4.69) 300(4.35)	6.3 & 6.4 (2 C-5 OCH ₃ , 2s); 4.9 (2 CH ₂ Ph, hump); 4.18 & 4.27 (α -H & α' -H, 2s); 2.4-3.5 (ArH, 36H, m).	—
19	236	C, 84.39 H, 6.71 N, 3.22	C ₆₀ H ₅₈ N ₂ O ₃	C, 84.50 H, 6.57 N, 3.29	225(4.65) 280(4.84)	—	—
20	174	C, 84.61 H, 6.43 N, 3.18	C ₆₀ H ₅₆ N ₂ O ₃	C, 84.50 H, 6.57 N, 3.29	224(4.64) 280(4.82)	9.3, 8.8, 8.3 & 5.72 (two <i>n</i> -Butyl, m, m, m & hump); 6.34 & 6.42 (two C-5 OCH ₃ , 2s); 4.17 & 4.29 (α -H & α' -H, 2s); 1.46-3.3 (ArH, 30H, m).	852 (M ⁺) (91%), 524 (M-C ₂₃ H ₂₂ NO) (22%), 419 (M-C ₃₀ H ₂₇ NO ₂) (100%).
21	212	C, 84.28 H, 6.47 N, 3.32	C ₅₈ H ₅₂ N ₂ O ₃	C, 84.47 H, 6.31 N, 3.40	222(4.74) 280(4.88)	—	—

* UV Spectra of 19 and 20 were recorded in dioxan.

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References

1. N. V. KONINKLIJKE, *Pharmaceutische Fabriken Voorheen Brocades-Stheeman and Pharmacia. Belg.*, 1964; 637, 354, *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, 62, 7729.
2. G. S. GADAGINAMATH and S. SIDDAPPA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 339.
3. H. BUDZIKIEWICZ, C. DJERASSI and D. H. WILLIAMS, "Mass Spectrometry of Organic Compounds", Holden-Day, Inc., San Francisco and London, 1967, p. 227.
4. C. R. NABAYANAN and K. N. Iyer, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1965, 3741.
5. K. Biemann, "Mass Spectrometry", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962, p. 123.